

PATRIOTISM OF MILITARY SERVANTS AND ITS SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL BASES

¹Tursunmurad Doniyorovich Mamatqabilov, ²Dilnoza Dilshod qizi Sayfullayeva,
³Abdukadirova Rano Yulchibayevna

¹Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan Associate Professor of the Department of National
Pride and Military Patriotism of the Academy, candidate of political sciences

²teacher of the University of world economy and diplomacy

³The Member of the Democratic Party "Milliy Tiklanish", Deputy of People's Deputies Uchtepa
District Council, 129 school principal

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10655029>

Abstract. *In historical experiences, the protection of man, society and the state and the realization of peace and stability in the country as a supreme blessing through social and spiritual-educational support of military personnel in the new Uzbekistan, the importance of every citizen living in the country to live and work with a sense of belonging is reflected in the article.*

Keywords: *historical experience, activities of military personnel, spiritual and educational work, social and cultural life, patriotism.*

As a person realizes himself as a living soul, in addition to natural disasters, he begins to feel fear of other living predators. In order to avoid the first cold and not to be attacked or victimized by any other creature, the act of self-defense begins. This means that in the process of realizing himself as a living being and trying to survive, he realizes that he needs protection. Look at living beings, they all have their own protection. Naturally, living beings live alone, but no matter how much we observe, the vast majority of living beings in the world are socialized, live in groups, gangs and societies. So, as a result of evolution, i.e., through life experience, slowly, as a result of striving to survive, humanity consciously creates a protection system for the interests of its own space - society. In ancient times, we see that protection, that is, during the special arming of the herd, society, is connected with the sense of protection of these living souls, the herd, the society, the most intelligent person.

Man, as the most conscious creature, did not make weapons suitable for his time for his own protection, starting from taking a simple stone in his hand, he adapted it to a sword, bent a tree branch to make a bow, found metal to make a sword, after the invention of gunpowder, it is enough to mention the actions of defense and invasion for man. On the one hand it brought terror, on the other hand it led to great opportunities.

This is where action, intelligence, which started from a sense of protection, led not only to protection, but to invasion, and it became not just protection, but a way of life for humans and other savage living beings.

In its place, the state, which is the structure of the society, separated its strongest and most capable combat unit from the general labor process as a precautionary measure for protection in historical formations, organized a military army and turned them into an honorary part of the state. Because it became clear that this situation is often related to the issue of life and death. This armed and specially trained part of the society ensured the peace of the society and saved it from untimely losses. This section of society, reserved for precautionary measures, later took advantage of its opportunities to invade, and the society proceeded to justify it in some cases. You see, the honorable part of the society, which was organized for protection, started to become a danger for another society. In this way, the military system was established in the society, and it still exists in the world as an honorable part of the society at the same time, as well as a danger to another

society. However, in a conscious society, the military, as the most honorable part of their people, society, mainly performs a protective function, and therefore they are considered an honorable, specially socially provided and protected part of their society, people.

Therefore, from the pulpit of the 21st century, it can be said that today no nation, state, nation should be proud of its defense, not of its past invasions, and honor its army with its heroism in the defense of the Motherland. The heroism of Tomaris (Iron Girl) for his people is a supreme example of patriotism in the psychology of a person, while Shiroq's sacrifice of his life for the sake of a man and his country in defeating the enemy is a supreme psychological example. With this in mind, it is always emphasized that our armed forces, as an honorable part of our nation, should be ready and prepared for any external aggression under the leadership of our Commander-in-Chief. This, in turn, is directly related to the development of the new Uzbekistan's defense capabilities and the high combativeness of the Armed Forces, economic, political, strategic, military-technical and scientific power and potential, the cohesion of the people of Uzbekistan, and the upbringing of every citizen in the spirit of patriotism. Therefore, on February 23, 2018, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted a decision "On approving the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism".

With this, the Cabinet of Ministers emphasizes the unity of the people and our armed forces, the unity of their spiritual resources for the defense of the homeland. In its place, it is emphasized that education of patriotism in our youth goes back to history with deep roots, and we see the highest level and example of patriotism in our armed forces, that is, it is shown that our armed forces have always been an honorable and integral part of our nation.

Without forgetting the special importance of educating young people as defenders of the homeland, the Supreme Commander-in-Chief, taking into account psychological unity, taking into account the operational condition of our armed forces, their moral and educational preparation, "On the radical improvement of the system of raising the moral and educational level of the military personnel of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan" 2018- In accordance with the concept of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the Armed Forces system, which was adopted and introduced on this basis by the separate decision No. 3898 of August 4, "The Motherland is sacred, protecting it is an honorable duty!" the idea was put forward.

This decision was incorporated into the practical process of the armed forces system, and it was determined that every Friday of the week was designated as the "Day of Moral Elevation and Patriotism" and that the moral and spiritual training of military personnel should be encouraged.

The goal is to steadfastly protect the independence, territorial integrity, and peace of our people as the highest task. Wide-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to strengthen peace and stability, ensure human rights, freedoms and interests, comprehensively develop our country, and raise its prestige in the international arena.

The people and the armed forces are one body and soul. We clearly feel that our armed forces are shoulder to shoulder with their people in the events of Sardoba, the events of Karakalpakstan and other cases that happened in our country, and the reputation of the representatives of our armed forces among the population can be a confirmation of this.

This means that we can see that our nation and its honorable armed forces are always ready to protect the Motherland from all forces and accidents, being one body and soul with their people. Therefore, according to the seven priorities defined in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026, it is noted that educating the youth of our country in the spirit of military patriotism is one of the most important tasks. Our ancestors who lived in our great past, our great compatriots who defended our country from invaders in order to maintain the peace

of our people, fought valiantly against the enemy for the freedom of the Motherland - Spitamen, To'maris, (Iron Girl) Shiroq, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temir, Temur Malik, Bobir, Shaibani Khan and others. As for our historical and national representatives, in our recent history, including Madaminbek and Ibrahim Korboshi, who fought for the honor of our country, the current defenders of the country have left their historical traces in their homeland.

Nowadays, our Armed Forces have improved organizationally and structurally, the mobility of the structures, the combat ability, the physical and moral training of the military, and the attitude of our people and especially the youth towards our military confirmed this.

Military units and units are regularly supplied with modern weapons and combat equipment. The work carried out in military educational institutions and directly in military units in order to fill our national army with highly skilled personnel, to further improve the training, knowledge and skills of military personnel is commendable.

At this point, we can proudly say about the research and practical work carried out at the Academy of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan.

The head of our state made it a task to constantly pay attention to the improvement of the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. Emphasizing that the scale of the work carried out in the troops of the Ministry of Defense on the organization of military-patriotic and spiritual-educational activities aimed at increasing the sense of pride of the military personnel in their national and cultural heritage on the example of the great thinkers of the Uzbek people, saying that "There is no military thought without military knowledge" said.

The patriotism shown by the military does not go unnoticed by our people, therefore, the issues of social protection of military personnel, correction of family conditions, and provision of housing are being implemented step by step. Such events serve to increase the prestige of the military service and further increase the combat readiness of our Armed Forces. These events are the main examples of how our troops and people work as one body and soul for the defense of the Motherland.

Another example of honoring our people's troops is certainly the decision "On additional measures for social support of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their family members" by creating facilities for the children of military servicemen on the basis of a state grant for full-time undergraduate courses in higher educational institutions additional admission quotas based on the state grant were allocated in the amount of five percent of the total admission quotas. Also, the necessary conditions for ensuring the health of military personnel and their family members are created, and families in need of housing are provided with housing in the prescribed manner. All this is a confirmation that our people and our army are one body and soul in the organization of homeland defense.

Based on our national mentality, even if there is only one son in the family and the rest are girls, these young men are given the privilege of serving in the area where their parents live, have a positive recommendation, and have completed at least two years of service in the military rank given because there are no vacant positions. privileges were created such as the granting of a title, additional vacations of 5, 10, 15 days each year according to the calendar of years of service.

Strong social protection, in turn, creates the ground for our officers and soldiers to serve with dedication, devotion to duty, and to improve their professional training. As a result of the comprehensive measures taken, the approach of the defenders of the Motherland to military service has been fundamentally changed, responsibility and discipline have been strengthened in the military units, and the feeling of pride and pride in the Motherland has increased in the hearts of all servicemen. In particular, in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, examinations for

the title of master of their profession are regularly held, and our soldiers and officers are achieving high marks.

It is known that military service is not without various risks, therefore, the head of our state, by a separate decision, provides for the payment of benefits to servicemen (employees) who were injured while performing their duties in the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan or to the family members of deceased (deceased) servicemen (employees), medical relevant decisions were also made about the organization and implementation of the inspection, the procedure for providing financial assistance to those who want to get accommodation.

Today's world is experiencing an information onslaught. For this reason, information acquisition is becoming one of the most urgent issues in the minds of not only the population, but also military personnel. Now, while analyzing the interest, mood, and social status of all personal content and social groups, it is necessary to master the skills of analyzing the sphere of influence of extremists and foreign, destructive ideas [1, p.1-3].

In this place, military life in our national army is organized taking into account that representatives of different nationalities and peoples serve. Because ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our country is the priority of our state policy. Representatives of more than 130 nationalities and peoples living in our country have united in 138 national and cultural centers and live peacefully as children of a big family under the motto "Uzbekistan is our common home". At the root of this is a great humanitarian policy. Therefore, by a separate decree, the Committee on International Relations and Friendly Relations with Foreign Countries was established under the Cabinet of Ministers. The main goal of this was to make a moral contribution to ensuring harmony in the military system by consistently continuing the state policy aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and tolerance in our society.

In today's world, where the process of globalization has intensified, global competition and mutual opposition are growing, threats such as radicalism, terrorism, extremism, proselytism, and "mass culture" are expanding, we must always be alert and vigilant. This is a psychological necessity of a person in the process of living in society.

That is why, paying close attention to the defense sector as well as all fronts, the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said that there will be such problems that they will always remain relevant. Among them, tasks such as spiritual and moral improvement of a person, pride in our national army, instilling a deep sense of responsibility for the protection of state security, forming a conscious attitude and an active life position in relation to the processes of globalization taking place in the world and around us are defined [2, p.3 -4]. Therefore, as the unity of the people and the army increases, the great work done by our people in the military field on a large scale increases strict discipline, spiritual and educational thinking in the army, and increases psychological unity in the understanding of the people and the army.

In conclusion, the moral and spiritual training of military personnel and the spiritual influence of the concept of the people and the army occupy a very important place.

As stated by the head of state, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, our country continues to strengthen its position in the world on the basis of the principle of "People and army - one body and one soul".

REFERENCES

1. Mamatqabilov T.D. "Combat readiness is a product of spiritual and educational training." New Uzbekistan newspaper, January 11, 2023.

2. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Part of the introduction. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2023. - B.3-4.
3. Sayfullayeva D. D. Q. THE EDUCATIONAL VALUE OF WORKS CREATED ON CHILDREN'S STORIES //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 252-257.
4. T. Mamatqabilov, M. Isaeva, N. Vahabov, D. Sayfullayeva SOCIAL AND SPIRITUAL FOUNDATIONS OF PATRIOTISM IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN // SAI. 2024. №B1. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/social-and-spiritual-foundations-of-patriotism-in-the-new-uzbekistan> (дата обращения: 08.02.2024).
5. Mamatqabilov T. et al. OVERCOMING GLOBAL PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. B10. – С. 230-234.